

THE ROLE OF THE THERMAL INDUCED RESIDUAL STRESSES IN A SINGLE FIBRE THERMOPLASTIC MODEL COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY

In this paper, the introduction of the thermal induced residual stresses into a single fibre composite was investigated by phase-stepping photoelasticity.

It has been demonstrated that stress transfer occurs through a thermally induced interfacial shear stress. On the axial loading of the composite, the stress at which the birefringence is extinguished can be used to estimate the magnitude of the interfacial shear stress.

Keywords: residual stress, glass fibre, polyamide, stress transfer mechanism

INTRODUCTION

Short glass fibre reinforced thermoplastic (SFRT) composite materials are widely used for the manufacture of complex shaped moulding, with higher performance than those from non-reinforced plastics. The mechanical properties of SFRT depend on the orientation and distribution of the discontinuous fibres[1] as well as the strength of the interface bonding[2] between the fibres and matrix.

The mechanism of micro-failure in SFRT has been described by Curtis[3] and Sato[4] based on direct microscopic observation. A detailed description of the initiation of micro-cracks and their propagation within the composite was revealed in their experiments. These effects have been described using the stress transfer between a single embedded short fibre and matrix using a shear-lag model[5] or finite element calculation[6].

However, a significant level of thermal residual stress can be induced in a SFRT and during cooling after manufacture. This plays a very important role in the fracture of the material[7].

Since there is a large difference between the thermal expansion coefficients of the fibres and the polymeric matrix, the fibres are put into compression on cooling. In addition, compressive stresses from the matrix are acting at the fibre matrix interface at radial direction.

Therefore, thermally induced residual stresses need to be included in micro-mechanical models. Attempts have been made to measure the magnitude of thermal residual stresses [8, 9]. Zhao et al [11] have reported the generation of thermal induced interfacial shear stresses through thermal loading of an embedded short fibre in an epoxy matrix.

In this paper we expand this work to a thermoplastic matrix system. The generation of thermal induced residual shear stress around a single glass fibre in a thermoplastic matrix has been studied. The extinction of the birefringence around the fibre on application of an axial load is reported. Phase-stepping photoelasticity has been used to quantify the magnitude of the shear stress along the interface.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Fibres for Photoelasticity Studies

Continuous water sized E-glass fibres were supplied by Owens Corning. “As received” water sized glass fibres were dried in a vacuum oven for 48 hour. A long control fibre was then cut by a knife manually into several pieces. Short fibres were immersed in 1% γ -aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APS) (GE Speciality) aqueous solution at a pH of 10.6 for 15 minutes and then washed in deionized water at 50°C for 24 h. They were then dried at room temperature in a vacuum oven. These glass fibres were referred to as “end-silanized” glass fibres.

The remaining silanized short glass fibres were cut again to obtain the unsilanized surfaces at the top of the fibre-ends. These short glass fibres were called “end-unsilanized” glass fibres.

The mechanical properties of silanized fibres were measured by single fibre tensile tests. The fibre strength and Weibull Modulus of the silanized glass fibre are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of single glass fibres used in the experiments

	Fibre strength (GPa)	Weibull Modulus
End-silanized fibre	1.63±0.7	2.99

Polymer Matrix

Amorphous polyamide (APA-Grilamid TR55 supplied by EMS-Grivory) was chosen as the matrix because of its transparency and non-crystallinity. Dog-bone shape polyamide specimens were prepared from the APA granules by injection moulding. The specimens were then stored in a dry vacuum at room temperature.

The mechanical properties of TR55 amorphous polyamide material are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Mechanical properties of amorphous polyamide (APA)

Tensile stress at yield (MPa)	Elongation at yield (%)	Modulus (GPa)
62.7±0.7	11.6±0.1	1.8±0.1

Sample Preparations for Photoelasticity Test

In order to embed a short glass fibre into a dog-bone shaped polyamide specimen, a deep nick was cut into the middle of the specimen surface to form a thin “pocket”. Then a short glass fibre (length $\approx 3\mu\text{m}$) was placed in the pocket (Figure 1) and the entire dog-bone shape sample was heated on a hotplate in a female mould at 213°C . A dog-bone shape male mould was placed on the top of polyamide specimen to provide a constant pressure. Specimen was heated for 20 minutes to ensure that the embedded glass fibre was fully melted by the polyamide. After that, the specimen was removed from the mould and cooled down to room temperature. The specimens were stored under vacuum at room temperature to avoid moisture absorption.

Figure 1 Schematic diagram of the method of embedding a short glass fibre into a polyamide specimen

Photoelasticity Experiment

A phase-stepping automated photoelasticity equipment was mounted on a micro-tensile test machine (Micromaterials Ltd, Wrexham, U.K.) to capture the photoelastic images during the real-time tensile testing. This equipment has four CCD cameras for collecting the photoelasticity images simultaneously at four different phase angles. Then 256×256 pixel images were transferred to a computer so that phase-stepping algorithms could be implemented.

The isoclinic angle θ and relevant retardation δ can be calculated using the unwrapping algorithms and procedures of Patterson and Wang [10].

$$\theta = \frac{1}{2} \tan^{-1} \frac{i_2 - i_3}{i_2 + i_3 - 2i_1} \quad (1)$$

$$\delta = \tan^{-1} \frac{i_2 - i_3}{\sin 2\theta (i_2 + i_3 - 2i_4)} \quad (2)$$

where i_1 to i_4 are the light intensities in 256×256 pixel images observed by the four CCD cameras. After the Retardation value was obtained, it can be algorithmed to the isochromatic fringe order value using the unwrapping procedure described by Patterson and Wang [10].

In photoelasticity, the difference between the principle stresses in a two-dimensional model can be related to the isochromatic fringe order according to equation 3 [13]. At a fibre-matrix interface, the principle stress difference ($\sigma_1 - \sigma_2$) will be dominated by the shear component so that the interfacial shear stress profiles at fibre/matrix interface can be obtained.

$$\frac{\tau_{max}}{2} = \frac{(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)}{2} = \frac{fN}{t} \quad (3)$$

where f is the photoelasticity constant, N is the fringe order and t is the thickness of specimen.

If a small-diameter inclusion was embedded into a relatively thick specimen, the observed principle stress difference varies through the thickness of the specimen. A correction of the maximum shear stress values around single fibre can be obtained from the analyses of Schuster[11] and Fiedler[12]

RESULTS

Contours maps of the relative retardations around the embedded glass fibres in an amorphous polyamide matrix are shown in Figure 2~5. The contour maps of the relative retardation show the birefringent patterns in the APA matrix, which indicates that the matrix was under stress before the uniaxial load was applied.

Figure 2 Contour map of the relative retardation around a short silanized glass fibre ($L_f=3.15\text{mm}$) in an amorphous polyamide matrix

Figure 4 Contour map of the relative retardation around a short silanized glass fibre ($L_f=2.88\text{mm}$) in an amorphous polyamide matrix

Figure 3 Contour map of the relative retardation around a short silanized glass fibre ($L_f=4.23\text{mm}$) in an amorphous polyamide matrix

Figure 5 Contour map of the relative retardation around a short silanized glass fibre ($L_f=2.56\text{mm}$) in an amorphous polyamide matrix

During photoelasticity experiment, the birefringent patterns in the APA matrix started moving from the middle of the fibre/matrix interface to the end of the fibre when a uniaxial tensile stresses was applied. Figure 6 shows the birefringent patterns movements around the end of short fibre in an APA matrix.

Figure 6 Birefringent patterns were moved to the end of fibre in an APA matrix when the applied uniaxial stress increased from 5 MPa to 8 MPa

Figure 7-Stage 1 shows that birefringent patterns stopped moving from the middle of the fibre/matrix interface to the fibre-end when the applied stress was continuously increased (applied stress: 15MPa, $L_f=4.23\text{mm}$). Then it was observed that no birefringent pattern appeared in the APA matrix under the polarized light when the applied stress increased from 15 to 16 MPa, as shown in Figure 7-Stage 2. Furthermore, the increased matrix stress caused birefringent patterns to be generated from the interface at the end of the fibre, which is shown in Figure 7-Stage 3.

Figure 7 Birefringent patterns were moved around a fibre end in a polyamide matrix when the applied uniaxial stress increased from 14 MPa to 20 MPa

In summary, the birefringent pattern movements in a short glass fibre embedded polyamide matrix can be described in three stages:

- 1) Stage 1: Birefringent patterns moving from the middle of the fibre/matrix interface to the end of the fibre.
- 2) Stage 2: Transition stage, no birefringent patterns showing in a polymer matrix
- 3) Stage 3: Birefringent patterns generating from the interface at the end of the fibre and moving from the fibre-end to the matrix.

In Stage 3, the birefringent patterns were found to appear either at the end of the fibre (Figure 8), or of the interface including the fibre-end (Figure 9).

Figure 8 Birefringent patterns generated around the end-unsilanized fibre end in a polyamide matrix

Figure 9 Birefringent patterns generated around the end-silanized fibre end in a polyamide matrix

DISCUSSION

Role of the Thermal Induced Residual Stresses

Because the birefringent pattern movements at the interface are corresponding to the principle stress difference in an APA matrix. The relevant retardations in an APA matrix around the fibre (Figure 2~5) are the indications of thermally induced stresses in a polyamide. The introduction of the thermal induced stresses, which is due to differential contractions of fibre and matrix during cooling, changes the stress transfer mechanism when external uniaxial tensile stress is applied to the matrix. In addition, the birefringent pattern movements shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7 represent the stress state difference under the applied matrix load.

In Stage 1, the thermal induced residual compression stress in the APA matrix is continuously compensating by the applied uniaxial tensile stress. Because of the stress

transfer between fibre and matrix, the interfacial shear component is also reduced, which causes the birefringent patterns move from the interface to the fibre-ends.

In Stage 2, the residual compressive stress in the matrix applied to the fibre is relieved by the stress transfer. Thus no shear stress is applied to the interface between the fibre and the matrix. As a result, the birefringent patterns are extinguished.

In Stage 3, birefringent patterns movement in the matrix implies that the transferring of tensile stress from the matrix to the fibre generates interfacial shear stress at the fibre/matrix interface.

In Stage 1, the polymer matrix in the vicinity of the fibre-ends is extended by the applied tensile stress, which could cause the occurrences of the debonding at the fibre-ends. Recent experimental results[13] have shown an improvement in the bonding between the fibre-ends and the matrix resulting in inhibition of debonding especially at the needle shaped fibre ends.

Figure 10 Birefringent patterns appeared at the fibre/matrix interface under 19 MPa applied stress

Figure 11 Birefringent patterns appeared at the interface around the fibre/matrix interface and the fibre-ends under 19 MPa applied stress

Residual Stress Measurement

The fringe order was analyzed after the birefringent pattern movements had been observed and recorded by phase-stepping photoelasticity. Figure 12 shows the changes in the fringe orders around a single fibre in an APA when the applied stress was increased. It was observed that the fringe order present at the fibre/matrix interface in the middle of the fibre. The fringe order then gradually moved to the end of the fibre and was extinguished at the fibre-end under applied matrix stress.

Figure 12 Fringe order changes around a single fibre in a polyamide matrix when the applied uniaxial stress increased

Based on the stress-optical law, the fringe order moves from the high principle stress difference to a low principle stress difference[14]. In the polymer matrix closed to the fibre/matrix interface within the stress transfer region, the principle stress difference can be regarded as the shear stress.

During the shear stress calculation by photoelastic method, the isoclinic angle and the relevant retardation values can be calculated using the light intensities in phase-stepping photoelastic images. Therefore, after an absolute fringe order for a pixel is obtained during real-time photoelasticity experiment, the compensated shear stress profile at the fibre/matrix interface can be obtained. Figure 13 shows the methodology for measuring the compensated shear stress at fibre/matrix interface.

Figure 13 Schematic diagram of the methodology for measuring the compensated interfacial shear stresses in a single fibre composite model

Figure 14 shows the results using the aforementioned “shear stress calculation” methodology. In the left hand side of the Figure 14, the contour map shows that the fringe orders in the matrix are higher than those of around the end of fibre. Therefore, the compensated shear stresses under applied matrix stress reaches to maximum in the middle of the fibre/matrix interface and gradually decreases along the fibre to the fibre-end.

Figure 14 Contour maps of fringe order and calculated shear stress profile at fibre/matrix interface in an amorphous polyamide matrix around a square shaped E-glass fibre-end at 7 MPa applied stresses

CONCLUSIONS

This paper illustrates the stress states in a short fibre embedded amorphous polyamide composite when the thermal induced residual stress is presented. In addition, a methodology based on the photoelastic analysis is demonstrated to evaluate the magnitude of interfacial thermal stresses in thermoplastic matrix composites.

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